

Advances in Plant-Mediated ZnO Nanoparticles: Synthesis Mechanisms, Functional Applications, and Environmental Implications-A Review

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ABSTRACT

Scientists are increasingly drawn to zinc oxide nanoparticles because of their exceptional properties and broad range of potential applications. A variety of physical and chemical methods are employed for the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles. Over time, these methods exert adverse effects on the environment due to their reliance on hazardous chemicals and energy-intensive processes; consequently, green synthesis has emerged as a more environmentally sustainable alternative. Green synthesis utilizes natural sources including microorganisms, fungi, algae, and different plant parts such as roots, leaves, flowers, seeds, and fruits. The phytochemicals found in green sources like phenols, flavonoids, terpenes, and alkaloids reduces (Zn^{2+} to Zn) and also help to stabilise the metal ions, which reduces the need for synthetic additions. To get the idea about the morphology, shape, nanoparticle size, crystal structure, elemental composition of synthesized NPs various characterization techniques can be used such as transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), UV-visible spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), and X-ray diffraction (XRD) enable researchers to better understand the behaviour and development of these nanoparticles. ZnO nanoparticles have shown a wide range of applications, including use as photocatalysts and as antimicrobial, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and anticancer agents, as well as in various biomedical applications. However, recent studies have raised concerns regarding their potential toxicity, emphasizing the need for further research to fully elucidate their biological effects. These NPs are toxic for water bodies and affect our ecosystem, even enter in human bodies and cause severe diseases like cancer. In light of the field's ongoing development, this review highlights the need to address safety and toxicity while summarising current knowledge on the green synthesis of ZnO NPs using plant-based methods and exploring their various applications.

Keywords: Zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnONPs); Synthesis; characterization; application; toxicity.

Graphical Abstract:

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

A broad and exciting discipline of science, nanotechnology presents fresh opportunities for knowledge and solution-oriented understanding of contemporary issues. It helps us to investigate our surroundings at the nanoscale and create wiser, more effective answers to present issues. Nowadays, nanoparticles are a necessary component of everyday living [1][2]. In every step of life, there is a use of nanotechnology. It is everywhere, even in our toothpaste, sleeping mattresses, eating processed foods, makeup items, electronics, and medicines. Our planet is basically becoming more and more entangled with nanotechnology. Fascinatingly, the idea of nanomaterials is not new at all. Unknowingly, in ancient civilisations, there was a use of nanoparticles in glass colouring, ceramic dyes, and black ink pigments [3][4]. For instance, the microscopic structures on the feet of insects and geckos help them to stick to vertical surfaces [5][6]. Comparably, the vivid colours of butterfly wings result from nanostructured patterns [7]. Natural nanofibers are present in spider silk [8][9]. Lotus leaf self-cleaning power comes from a mixture of micro-protrusions and nano-hairs. Scientists find inspiration for replicating and improving these natural occurrences of nanostructures for various technological uses [10][11]. A wide range of nanomaterials is present around us, so their classification is important for their detailed study. Nanomaterials are classified on different bases, such as based on their origin, which can be natural, like protein, minerals, milk, etc., and synthetic nanoparticles like quantum dots, metal oxide nanoparticles. On the structural configuration basis, it can be classified as organic, inorganic, carbon, and based on the number of dimensions, it can be 0D,1D, 2D,3D. With the advancement in technology, different techniques for characterization of nanoparticles are used, like X-Ray diffraction analysis (XRD), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), UV-Visible spectroscopy, scanning electron microscopy (SEM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), etc. By the use of these advanced techniques, researchers are trying to find out the exact mechanism of nanoparticle synthesis. Recent studies shows that zinc oxide nanoparticles have application in different fields such as photocatalysts, antimicrobials, antioxidants,

antidiabetics, anticancer agents and many are still left to find out [12][13][14][15].

Zinc oxide nanoparticles have a great potential to fulfil all the desired applications as a metal oxide nanoparticle, even though it is the second most abundant metal oxide nanoparticle after iron. By changing the morphology, the physical and chemical behaviour of these nanoparticles can be changed. It is a white powder with insoluble properties in water. Metal oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles have been synthesized by using different methods, such as physical, chemical, and biological. Two synthesis approaches like top-down and bottom-up approaches, are used for the synthesis of nanoparticles but plant mediated green synthesis of metal oxide nanoparticles is a better option among all [16][17][18]. Researchers had an idea about the potential of biological methods due to the great success of the synthesis of plant-mediated metal oxide nanoparticles. Phytochemicals present in plants act as reducing as well as stabilizing agents which reduces the use of chemicals and energy consumption, making it environmentally friendly also [19][20]. It is comparatively cheap, easy to synthesize, shows various applications in different fields, and is safe due to these properties, making it researchers' first choice as a metal oxide nanoparticle. It is a good n-type semiconductor which helps it to have better electrical and optical properties [21]. It has a high mechanical and thermal stability at room temperature. Due to these properties, it can be used for energy storage, laser technology, in solar cells, sensors, as a photocatalyst, energy generator, supercapacitor, etc. Not only is this because of its comparatively low toxicity and high UV absorption values, which help to use it in drug delivery and the biomedical field. Because of strong resistance to microbes and being soluble in acidic environments, it is extensively used in biological labelling and sensing, gene and drug delivery [22],[23]. ZnO NPs are also used in photocatalytic degradation, textile industry, packaging, cosmetics, defence, and security purposes. According to recent research, nanoparticles can also be prepared by the breakdown of natural minerals via water droplets. In the future, researchers can find many other applications in different fields [24],[25].

Due to the nano range, there are various applications of zinc oxide NPs that can be observed, but at the

same time, their toxic effect cannot be ignored. There are lots of sources for the generation of NPs, natural like volcanic eruption, forest fire, and ocean water evaporation, etc., as well as man-made. Toxic effects can be seen on algae, plants, microorganisms, and mammals, mainly on the liver, kidneys, lungs, spleen tissues, reproductive health, and the environment. According to recent studies, the exact mechanism of toxicological effect is not clear yet, but the solubility of ZnO NPs is one of the main reasons for its toxic effect. Oxidative toxicological mechanisms and these effects are dependent on their stability, concentration, their physicochemical properties like specific surface area, metal involved, size, different exposure routes, oral administration, dermal contact, and inhalation. Application of ZnO-NPs in biomedicine fields, such as cancer diagnosis and therapy, causes direct human exposure and could be the main reason for toxicity. Zinc oxide and titanium oxide nanoparticles are commonly used in cosmetics like sunscreen, ointments, etc., and can easily enter our cells and induce oxidative stress. Excessive use of nanoparticles for the production of textiles is not completely beneficial. Toxic chemicals also used during the production of these smart fibers and nanoparticles can leach out from the final product and can easily enter the water bodies. Nanoparticles on a few species, like zebrafish, are also observed, according to research, “embryo toxicity test” exposed that zinc oxide nanoparticles killed zebrafish embryos and affected our ecosystem [26],[27].

2. Synthesis of zinc oxide nanoparticles

For the synthesis of nanoparticles, (as shown in Figure 1) there are different approaches, such as the top-down approach and the bottom-up approach, which give desired-sized nanoparticles. The top-down approach involves the disintegration of material from a higher level to smaller and the bottom-up approach involves the aggregation of material from smaller levels [28],[29]. The main difference between these two approaches is that, in the first one, bulk material is used as a starting material, and after that, the particle size of the bulk material is reduced by different methods, such as physical, mechanical, and chemical. On the other side, in the second approach, small atom aggregates form clusters and finally turn out into nanoparticles [30].

Figure 1: Synthesis of ZnO NPs via top-down and bottom-up approach

2.2 Different methods to prepare nanoparticles:

1. *Physical methods:* Nanomaterials and nanocomposites can be synthesized by mechanical mining, Thermal Evaporation-Condensation, Sputtering Method, Plasma Method, Pulsed Laser Ablation Method, Explosion and Nano lithographic techniques etc. Generally, physical methods to prepare nanoparticles are not preferred because they require complex equipment, high energy, and ultimately become an expensive option [31],[32],[33].
2. *Chemical methods:* Zinc oxide nanoparticles can also be synthesized by different chemical methods, such as the precipitation method, colloidal method, sol-gel method, hydrothermal method, solvothermal method, etc. (as shown in Figure 2) In the case of this technique, there is a requirement of special conditions like high pressure, temperature, and chemicals, etc., and because of the excess use of chemicals, it is not environmentally friendly [34],[35],[36].
3. *Biological methods:* In the last few decades, the use of this method has grown too fast. Common terms used for this method are green synthesis. The reason behind this growth is that it reduces the toxicity of the manufacturing process as well as the final product by using the least amount of chemicals not requires any special condition like high temperature and pressure [37],[38],[39],[40].

2.2.1 Different sources for green synthesis of nanoparticles:

- 1. Bacteria:** Zinc oxide nanoparticles can be synthesized by bacteria. Hu et al. synthesized ZnO nanoparticles using bacterial cellulose [41],[42]. Bairavi et al. have biosynthesised Novel Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) using Endophytic Bacteria *Sphingobacterium thalophilum* [43]. This method is used for the synthesis of many nanoparticles, but because of some issues like culture contamination, lengthy procedures, and less control over the size of nanoparticles, bacteria are not commonly used for the green synthesis of nanoparticles [44].
- 2. Fungi:** They are a good source for the green synthesis of nanoparticles [45]. Nehru et al. synthesized ZnO-NPs by using the endophytic fungal extract of *Xylaria arbuscula* [46]. Kamal et al. prepared bioinspired bimetallic iron and zinc oxide nanoparticles by using mushroom extract [47]. Mohamed et al. investigate that the fungal strain impacts the shape, bioactivity, and multifunctional properties of green-synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles [48]. Commercial quantities of nanoparticles can be synthesized by the use of fungi.
- 3. Algae:** These are also used for the synthesis of nanoparticles. Azizi et al. biosynthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles using brown marine macroalga *Sargassum muticum* aqueous extract [49]. Priyadarshini et al. synthesized metallic silver and zinc oxide nanoparticles using macroalgae (*Gracilaria edulis*) extracts [50]. But green synthesis of nanoparticles by using algae is not very popular.
- 4. Plants:** Different parts of plants, like roots, stems, leaves, fruits, and flowers, have been used for the synthesis of nanoparticles [51]. The phytochemicals present in these plant parts act as reducing and stabilizing agents. A huge number of syntheses have been reported from plant extracts. Vidya c. et al synthesized from leaf extract of jackfruit [52], Sohail et al. from neem leaf extract [53], *Myrica esculenta* fruit extract used by Sohan Lal et al. [54], Nava et al. used fruit peel extract in 2017 [55]. Countless research

studies exist in which plant extracts are used for the preparation of nanoparticles. Till now, this method is best among all, because it is nontoxic, cheap, and generally a one-pot synthesis. So, it takes comparatively less time and less harm to the environment [56].

Figure 2: Synthesis of ZnO-NPs via different physical, chemical and biological methods.

2.3 Biogenic mechanism of nanoparticle formation via plants

There are two basic components that are important for the plant-mediated green synthesis of nanoparticles: the first one is the plant extract and the metal salt. In plant parts (leaves, fruits, flowers etc.) phytochemicals are present like polyphenols, carotenoids, antioxidants, flavonoids, anthocyanins, terpenes, alkaloids, etc. acts as active agents which actually help in reduction and also act as stabilizing agents. It reacts with a metal salt and synthesizes a nanoparticle. Redox potential of phytochemicals present in a plant extract is a very important factor; it actually decides the extent of reduction. It can be influenced by various factors like chemical reaction condition (pH, concentration, temperature, reaction time), functional groups, electron-donating or electron-withdrawing substituents. Md Jahidul Haque explained the mechanism of nanoparticles synthesis by using neem leaf extract [57]. Busila et al. suggested that the aldehyde group present in neem leaves is responsible for the reduction and stabilization of zinc oxide to zinc oxide nanoparticles [58] (shown in Figure 3). After that, many researchers gave their opinion according to their studies. Osuntokun et al. studied that the hydroxyl group on phenolic MO present in *Brassica oleracea* L. var. *italica* could

combine with Zn^{2+} of $ZnCl_2$ to convert $Zn(OH)_2$, and after calcination, converts into nanoparticles [59]. Phytochemicals like flavonoids contain various functional groups, which have a tendency to reduce metal ions. Ahmed et al. used medicinal plant basil and said that the enol to keto transformation is the major factor in the synthesis of nanoparticles [60]. Moringa oleifera extract used by Matinise et al. found that $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ gives Zn^{2+} in solution, l-ascorbic acid in Moringa oleifera oxidised to l-dehydroascorbic acid via free radicals. Zn^{2+} and l-ascorbic acid anions are attracted by electrostatic interaction and form Zn-ascorbic acid complex, and after high temperature calcination, form nanoparticles [61]. Altemimi et al. proposed that phytochemicals present in aqueous leaf extract of phoenix roebeleii palm,

reduced Zn^{2+} to Zn^0 , which reacts with dissolved oxygen, converts into nanoparticles, and then are capped with active phytochemicals to prevent agglomeration, increasing the stability of nanoparticles [62]. Sutradhar et al. suggested that generally phytochemicals present in plant extract (tomato) reduced Zn^{2+} to Zn^0 , which reacts with dissolved oxygen, phytochemicals act as a stabilizing agent to convert it finally into nanoparticles [63]. Alamdari et al. prepared Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles using the leaf extract of *Sambucus ebulus* and tried to investigate the possible mechanism of synthesis [64]. But the complete mechanism is not clearly understood yet; for this reason, it attracts the attention of many researchers [65],[66],[67].

Figure 3: (a) Mechanism of size reduction and stabilization of ZnO NPs during the biosynthesis fabrication by using Neem leaf extract [57], (reprinted with the permission of ref. No. 57, under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.) (b) Proposed mechanism of synthesized ZnO NPs via different biological compounds [61]. (Reprinted with the permission of ref. No. 61)

2.4 Key parameters shaping the formation and properties of nanoparticles

Several factors affect the preparation and properties of nanoparticles, some of them are the method of preparation, Concentration, pH of the medium, and pressure. of metal salt (influences particle size the most), contact time, temperature (calcination temperature), environment, pore size, particle shape etc. [68],[69].

1. **Method of preparation and concentration of sample:** There are different methods used for the synthesis of nanoparticles, such as physical, chemical, and biological. All these methods have their own merits and demerits, but due to less use of chemicals and an environmentally friendly

biological method, it is the better option among the traditional options. In the case of plant-mediated synthesis of nanoparticles, the/ type of plant extract is important; plant extract serves two roles: it acts as a reducing agent as well as a stabilizing agent. The type of phytochemical present in plant extract affects the appearance of NPs. The concentration of the sample also affects the properties of NPs differently [70].

2. **Effect of pH of medium on synthesis and properties of NPs:** pH is a very important factor that affects the synthesis of NPs, especially those synthesized by plant extract. The shape and size of NPs can be changed by changing the pH [71]. pH 12 is the preferred pH for the synthesis of ZnO-NPs. Many researchers tried to synthesize ZnO-NPs at

different pH levels, but they found that pH 12 is best; at this pH, the ratio of hydroxyl ions// (phytochemicals present in plant extract) to hydrogen ions was optimum. According to Siswanto et al. at pH 7, ZnO nanoparticles are not fully formed, at pH 8, the NPs have not formed, and other compounds. At a pH 10, the formation of ZnO nanoparticles started, whereas at pH 12 pure ZnO nanoparticles had formed [72]. Mechai et al. explained by FTIR analysis, at pH(x) before calcination, there is a minimum change in the peaks

related to O-H and C-H functional groups. After calcination, the peak related to the O-H functional groups diminished, showing a reduction or removal of these groups at high temperatures during the calcination process. As the pH increased to 13, these peaks diminished, shows a reduction in the concentration of O-H functional groups shown in (Figure 4). These spectral changes highlight a transformation in the material's chemical composition [73].

Figure 4: (a) Raman analysis of NP size distribution of hyd.C, RT.pH(x), and RT.pH(x)[73], (b) FT-IR spectra of ZnO NPs at different pH [73]. (Reprinted with the permission of reff. No. 73, under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.)

3. Effect of Temperature: It also a very important factor for all types of synthesis. Generally high temperature is required for physical methods as compare to chemical and biological. At different temperature shape and size of synthesized nanoparticles can be different. Kotresh et al. synthesized NPs by coprecipitation method and discussed how temperature affects the size of NPs [74]. Manzoor et.al. observed that if synthesis

temperature increases from 65^oC to 75^oC then there would be systematic change in particle size, crystallinity, and optical properties [75]. Basri et al. explained the effect of temperature by NPs derived from pineapple peel extract [76]. Salahuddin et al. prepared ZnO NPs and characterize by XRD. XRD patterns of wurtzite ZnO NPs (Z₂- Z₇) obtained from the annealing of ZnO precursor at different temperatures [77], (shown in Figure 5)

Figure 5: (a) XRD pattern of ZnO NPs synthesized with heating (60 °C) and without heating (28 °C) [76], (b) UV-vis absorption spectra of ZnO NPs, prepared at different annealing temperatures Z₂, Z₃, Z₄, Z₅, Z₆, and Z₇ [77]. (reprinted with the permission of reff. No. 76 and 77)

2.5 Other factors that affect the synthesis and properties of NPs.

Pressure affects the shape and size of NPs, at an ambient pressure rate of reduction of metal ions by plant-mediated synthesis will be maximum. Similarly, the quality of synthesized NPs also depends on time, it can affect the potential of NPs. The environment can also affect the nature of these NPs. Nucleation time also affects the shape and size of synthesized NPs. UV

and XRD data support that if the size of NPS decreases, the crystallinity will also decrease [78].

3. Characterization of synthesized nanoparticles:

Characterization of nanoparticles is a very important step in the preparation of nanoparticles. Different techniques (as given in Table 1) have been used to characterize the nanoparticles like XRD, EDAX, FT-IR, DLS, XPS, UV-VIS Spectroscopy, Raman, TEM, SEM, FMR, NTA, DCS etc. [79],[80].

Table 1: Information derived from different techniques:

S.No	Technique used for the characterization of NPs	Basic-Information derived from different techniques	References
1	X-ray Diffraction (XRD)	Crystal structure	[81]
2	Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS)	Detects aggregation	[82]
4	Ferro Magnetic Resonance (FMR)	Crystallographic defects	[83]
5	Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)	Morphology	[84]
6	Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)	Nanoparticle size	[85]
7	UV-Visible Spectroscopy (UV-Vis)	Optical properties	[86]
8	Fourier Transfer Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)	Surface composition	[87]
9	X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)	Electronic structure	[88]
10	NMR (nuclear magnetic resonance)	Molecular structure	[89]
11	Electro-kinetic Potential (Zeta potential)	Surface charge	[90]

3.1 X- ray diffraction (XRD): This technique is used in the characterization of almost all NPs, it can deduce the crystal structure, lattice parameter, composition(elemental-chemical), and grain size of NPs. One of the best things about this technique is, sample is used in powder form after drying. This technique is not that informative for amorphous materials. The particle size of the sample can be calculated by using Scherrer's equation. By using reference patterns available from the International Center for Diffraction Data (ICDD). The composition of particles can be determined by comparing the position and intensity of the peaks [81]. Chaudhari et al. prepared ZnO NPs and observed that the synthesized NPs have a hexagonal wurtzite structure and a crystallite size is 36.18 nm [91], [92]. Salahuddin et al. prepared ZnO NPs via the

precipitation method and characterize by XRD [77]. Talam et al. characterize ZnO NPs by XRD by explaining its diffraction peak values, its shape, and calculate its diameter by the Debye-Scherrer formula and average size [93]. Arora et al. characterize ZnO NPs, calculate their shape and size (50 nm) by the Debye-Scherrer formula [94]. Abdelbaky et al. synthesized ZnO Nanoparticles by using *Pelargonium odoratissimum* (L.) aqueous leaf extract, and different peak values in the XRD pattern gave the idea of a structure that is hexagonal wurtzite, and the particle size is 14 nm [95]. Aldalbahi et al. synthesized nanoparticles by using aqueous extract of *Kalanchoe blossfeldiana* and used the XRD technique to find out the size and shape of nanoparticles [96] (shown in Figure 6)

Figure 6: (a) XRD pattern of ZnO nanoparticles [91], (b) The X-Ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles [92], (c) XRD pattern of biosynthesized ZnO NPs via *P. odoratissimum* L. ALE [95], (d) XRD pattern of the synthesized ZnO NPs [96]. (reprinted with the permission of ref. No. 91, 92, 95 and 96 under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.)

3.2 UV- Visible spectroscopy: It gives an idea about the size, concentration, agglomeration state, and optical properties of NPs and hints at their shape. This technique works on the Beer-Lambert law. This technique allows the sample to be recovered after measurement, but this is a bulk technique that provides average information about the sample rather than individual NPs [86]. Abdelbaky et al.

studied the optical characteristics of green-synthesized ZnO NPs [95] (shown in Figure 7). A known amount of ZnO NPs (0.05 g) was dispersed in 5 mL of ethanol (96%). The absorption spectrum was recorded by using a UV-Vis spectrometer between a wavelength of 200–800 nm [96]. Satdev et al. characterize NPs by UV-VIS spectroscopy and observed a peak at 380 nm [97]

Figure 7: (a) UV-Vis spectrum of biosynthesized ZnO NPs via *P. odoratissimum* L. ALE [95], (b) UV-vis spectra of synthesized ZnO NPs (before annealing and annealed at 500 °C) [61], (c) UV-Vis absorbance spectra [73], (Reprinted with the permission of ref. No. 61, 73 and 95 under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.)

3.3 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR): It give information about the surface composition, functional group present in NPs, and ligand binding by using the beam of IR radiation. Frequency range is between 4000 - 600 cm^{-1} . FTIR spectrometer collects the interferogram, performs

a function, and displays the spectrum on screen. According to specific band values, a particular functional group can be identified [87]. Chaudhari et al. characterized by FTIR, observed different peaks, which confirm the presence of metal-oxygen (ZnO) stretching vibrations [91], (shown in Figure 8). Albarakaty et al. characterize the green NPs synthesized using aqueous seed extract,

showing different peaks, indicating the presence of a capping agent or bonded to the NPs surface [98].

Figure 8: (a) FTIR absorption spectra of ZnO NPs and ALE of *P. odoratissimum*[95], (b)FT-IR spectra of Moringa Oleifera extract and synthesized ZnONps (Before anneal and annealed at 500 °C) [61], (c) The FTIR spectra of ZnO nanoparticles [91]. (Reprinted with the permission of reff. No. 61, 91, and 95 under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.)

3.4 Scanning Electron Microscopy and Transmission Electron Microscopy (SEM & TEM):

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) can detect morphology, porosity, cracks, defects, secondary phases, dispersion of NPs in cells, and other matrices. Using an electron beam, it gives a high-resolution surface image used to learn about nanomaterials. Because of high magnification, its images are used to visualize the topography of the surface. Similarly, a transmission electron microscope (TEM) gives an idea about size, shape, and aggregation state. SEM gives information on the morphology of the sample. In this technique, when the electron beam interacts with the sample, diffraction takes place, and the diffraction strength

depends on the plane's orientation of the electron beam [84]. From some angles, the beam is diffracted from the axis, whereas from others it is transmitted. By blocking the electrons deflected and allowing the unscattered electron to pass through its light field, a dark field image can be obtained, and deflected electrons can also generate a dark field image. Albarakaty et al. analyze the shape and size of the green NPs synthesized using aqueous seed extract by TEM [98]. Geetha et al. synthesize ZnO nanoparticles by using the latex of *Euphorbia Jatropa* as a reducing agent [99]. Talam et al. show the size of the NPs is 10 nm by SEM, and its hexagonal structure is confirmed by TEM [93], (shown in Figure 9).

Figure 9: (a) [SEM micrographs](#) of un-doped ZnO [99], (b) HR-TEM images of biosynthesized ZnO NPs [95].(reprinted with the permission of reff. No. 98 and 95 under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.)

4. Applications of Zinc oxide nanoparticles

4.1 Photocatalytic Activity: Zinc oxide nanoparticles have a large surface area with a narrow bandgap. Due to this property, they absorb UV radiation very fast and decompose the substance [100]. Synthesized ZnO NPs from *Platanus orientalis* leaf extract used as a photocatalytic material for the

degradation of Acid Red 14 dye [101]. By using Neem and Eucalyptus leaf extract, synthesized ZnO nanoparticles were used as a photocatalytic material for the degradation of methylene blue dye [57]. ZnO nanoparticles efficiently degraded RhB dye in an aqueous solution under UV radiation [102]. Aldalbahi et al. explained that under UV radiation, green-synthesized ZnO NPs catalyze

show better performance. With time, the color and concentration of dye gradually decrease [96]. Faisal et al. explained the possible mechanism of the methylene blue dye. In the presence of ultraviolet light, dye is adsorbed on the surface of the catalyst to excite valence electrons so the electrons may transfer to the conduction band from the valence band. During the process, a positive hole h^+ is lifted inside the valence band. The

positive holes and free electrons will react on the surface of the photocatalyst along with adsorbed water molecules, hence the positive holes will react with water to produce $\cdot OH^-$ radicals, and the free electrons reduce the dissolved oxygen to superoxide anion $O_2^{\cdot -}$ radicals. These light-generated radicals degrade the dye molecules into simple molecules such as CO_2 and H_2O [103] (shown in Figure 10).

Figure 10: (a) Mechanism of the photocatalytic degradation of the synthesized ZnO NPs [96], (b) mechanism of the photocatalytic degradation of the MB and Eosin Y dyes by synthesized ZnO NPs [103]. Reprinted from ref. No. 96 and 103, under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.)

4.2 Antibacterial and Antifungal Activity: Bacteria are everywhere, and many are very dangerous for us. They can even survive in harsh conditions and reproduce easily; for this reason, many antibiotics are present in the market, but green-synthesized nanoparticles are a better option among them [104]. Citrus hystrix leaf extracts mediated Zinc oxide nanoparticles deliver prominent antibacterial activities against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* [105]. ZnO NPs exhibited higher antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria, especially *Escherichia coli*. These nanoparticles are the most widely researched metal oxide NPs for antifungal applications. Antifungal mechanism is based on the power of ZnO NPs to penetrate the fungal membrane by diffusion and endocytosis. If these NPs are present in the

cytoplasm, they disrupt the normal functioning of mitochondria, which generates the reactive oxygen species commonly known as ROS and releases Zn^{2+} ions, which actually causes permanent harm to DNA and the demise of the cell. Fungicides commonly used in agriculture are mainly made of zinc compounds [106]. Aluminum gum-stabilized ZnO nanoparticles were found to be a good antifungal agent against *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Candida albicans*, and *Penicillium varians*. The antibacterial effect of the biosynthesized ZnO NPs was evaluated by disc diffusion assay against *S. aureus*, *B. cereus*, and *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa* [107]. Abdelbakty et al. showed that biosynthesized ZnO NPs showed higher antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *B. cereus* compared to *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli* [98], (shown in Figure 11)

Figure 11: (a) Antibacterial activity of ZnO NPs synthesized from the aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* [108], (b) Mechanisms of ZnO NPs toxicity against bacteria [95]. Reprinted with the permission of ref. No. 108 and 95 under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license

4.3 Antidiabetic and Anticancer Activities: ZnO nanoparticles can also be used as an antidiabetic agent. Plant-mediated green-synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles had better anti-diabetic effect on streptozotocin (STZ) than that of bulk ZnO particles [109],[110]. Green synthesized zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs) from the leaves of *Raphanus sativus* var. *Longipinnatus* and the interpretation of its anticancer activity were studied [111]. Ln-ZnO NPs were effective in inhibiting the viability of human A549 lung cancer cells at higher concentrations of 80µg mL⁻¹. The morphological

changes in the Ln-ZnO NPs treated A549 lung cancer cells were observed under a phase contrast microscope. NPs exhibited significant antioxidant potential, which was studied to investigate the anticancer activity against Raw 264.7 and Caco-2 cancer cell lines [112],[113]. Anjum et al. explained that ZnO NPs show cytotoxicity in cancer cells due to the increased intracellular levels of dissolved zinc ions, followed by enhanced ROS production, causing cancer cell death via an apoptotic signaling pathway [114], shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: (a) A schematic representation of the overall cytotoxicity of ZnO nanoparticles, leading to cell death [113], (b) Possible mechanism of anticancerous activity of ZnO NPs [114]. Reprinted from ref. no 113 and 114 under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license)

4.4 Antioxidant: Antioxidant molecules can neutralize whenever there is an excess of free radicals present in the body. According to previous studies, ZnO NPs increases the activity of antioxidant enzymes and

decreases malonaldehyde which is responsible for oxidative stress [115]. So, this can shield the body from the destructive effects of oxidative stress. ZnO NPs found to have considerable antioxidant activity

against DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) free radicals. Results of antioxidant activity showed that increase in concentration of ZnO nanoparticles increases the radical scavenging activity [108],

(shown in Figure 13). [Abdelbaky](#) showed that the aqueous extract has a superior antioxidant potential to traditional reference L-ascorbic acid [95].

Figure 13: (a) In vitro antioxidant property of DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) [108], (b) DPPH FRSA of ZnO NPs, ALE and L-ascorbic acid at different concentrations [95]. reprinted with the permission of reff. No. 108 and 93 under Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license.

4.5 Textiles, Packaging and Cosmetics: The textile industry is growing day by day due to worldwide high demand for fibers. The modern textile industry has made changes according to the need and supply [116],[117]. There are many improvements in terms of its mechanical strength, surface texture, durability, etc. Nanotechnology incorporated fibers have many innovative applications, like in fashion, sports, advanced protection, health areas, pharmaceuticals, space suits, and transportation. There are a number of categories of smart textiles. Some of them are mentioned here: ultraviolet- resistant textiles, antimicrobial textiles, sensors on textiles, color-tunable optical fibres, electrically conductive textiles, energy storage by textiles, photonics in textiles, solar energy harvesting by textiles, and many more.[118],[119]. These nanoparticles widely use in packaging. Zinc oxide nanoparticles can also be used as a component in sunscreen and

in other cosmetics These nanoparticles have flexible structures that allow the control of physical characteristics, with enhanced surface properties, which provide a high applicability in dermo pharmacy and cosmetics [120],[121].

4.6 Solar cells and super capacitor: Green-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles used to fabricate dye-sensitized solar cells [122]. The increased effectiveness of the manufactured dye-sensitive solar cell is attributable to a large improvement in dye molecular adsorption onto the surface of ZnO NPs, shown in Figure 14 Thus, the usage of the green produced ZnO NPs for creating dye-sensitized solar cells is a simple and viable way for the well-being of our future [123],[124],[125]. Because of the unique characteristics of nanoparticles, researchers try to find applications of these ZnO NPs in every field. Nanocomposites can act as a promising electrode material for supercapacitor applications [126],[127]

Figure 14: Applications of zinc oxide nanoparticles.

5. Toxicity

Toxicity is an important consideration in discussions of nanoparticles. The toxicity of nanoparticles is largely dependent on their physical and chemical properties, such as shape, size, surface charge, stability, concentration, and bioavailability in biological systems, and they tend to accumulate in tissues or organ systems. There are many natural sources of NPs, such as anthropogenic activities, volcanic eruptions, forest fires, and ocean water evaporation, which produce large numbers of NPs. Among all types of nanoparticles, inorganic NPs like metallic oxide nanoparticles are the most commonly produced NPs. Green-synthesized zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were less toxic compared to those synthesized by the other conventional method, while the plant itself showed dose-dependent low toxicity [128]. Recent studies showed that nanoparticles can be absorbed, transported, and accumulated by terrestrial plants. The presence of nanoparticles in some edible plants may decrease harvests and affect human health. Among the various concentrations of ZnO NPs administered, 10 mg/ml or more caused deformities and a lower survival rate. ZnO NPs were found to influence the normal development of zebrafish embryos in a dose-dependent manner [129]. Heinlaan et al. also discussed the toxicity of nano- and bulk-sized ZnO to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* and crustaceans *Daphnia magna* and *Thamniccephalus platyurus*. [130].

Not only these organisms but human beings also get affected by these nanoparticles. Now days zinc oxide and titanium oxide nanoparticles commonly used in cosmetics like sunscreen, ointments etc. and can easily enter to our cells and induce oxidative stress. Excessive use of nanoparticles for the production of textiles is not completely beneficial. Toxic chemicals also used during the production of these smart fibers and nanoparticles can be leach out from the final product and can easily enter into the water bodies. Goetz et al. explained that in textile industry, the extent of leaching is dependent on the concentration of NPs, pH of water or sweat [131]. The medicinal application of nanoparticles is the root cause of

toxicity, undoubtedly it serves the positive impact in biomedical field but on the other hand it causes negative consequences which became a big threat now. In case of human beings, nanoparticles toxicity induced in nervous system, immune system, respiratory system, it decreases cognitive ability, and even affect embryonic development. According to khatab et al. generally, nanoparticles used in biomedical field can easily enter to our cells can cause membrane distortions. These nanoparticles interact with mitochondria and produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) and if enters to nuclei, then it can cause genotoxicity. ROS, inflammation, necrosis and apoptosis are key factors of toxicity caused by nanoparticles [132]. Crop plants and atmospheric nanoparticles interactions can cause NPs accumulation in crops, and can affect agricultural production and food safety negatively. Positively charged NPs causes growth inhibition, increased antioxidant enzyme activity, and altered gene expression and metabolite composition and even significantly changed the structure and composition of plants. From these researches it can be concluded that these NPs products become a direct source of pollution in environment and affects our ecosystem. Hence, there is a need of proper government regulations regarding the production and use of NPs. So, these developments can be done within the limits of environmental safety. All these discussions of nanoparticle toxicity emphasize their dual role in biomedical applications, where favorable outcomes are mostly coupled by possible detrimental effects. Therefore, understanding the underlying molecular pathways is crucial to better comprehending and reducing these harmful effects. In such cases, computational research can be an effective means of bridging the knowledge gap between microscopic mechanistic insights and macroscopic toxicity observations, shown in Figure 15 These methods make it possible to study molecular-level interactions between nanoparticles and biomolecules, membrane disruptions, the production of reactive oxygen species, etc. Nevertheless, a thorough discussion such computational approaches are beyond the scope of the present manuscript [133],[134],[135].

Figure 15: Schematic illustration of the toxicity responses and regulatory mechanisms of ZnO NPs in plants [134].

6. CONCLUSION

This review discusses the plant-mediated green synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles. This method is considered as better than other known methods because of less use of chemicals, it is environmentally friendly, and generally does not require any special conditions like high temperature and pressure. There is a huge biodiversity to explore and discover new sources that can be used for large-scale synthesis. Due to advancements in technology, there are lots of options for the characterization and detection of unique properties of synthesized nanoparticles. The exact mechanism of green synthesis of nanoparticles is also not known. Some researchers worked in this field and found the mechanism for a few plants. According to them, phytochemicals present in plant parts act as reducing as well as stabilizing agents, which actually reduces the chemical requirement. This area is still vacant for research, so there is a scope of research in this field to know exactly how phytochemicals present in different plant parts help in the synthesis of plant-mediated synthesis. A wide range of applications can be seen for metal oxide nanoparticles. Different bioactivity pathways were explained, especially metal oxide nanoparticle (ZnO-NPs), which show antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antioxidant, antiviral, orthopedic implants, wound healing, bone healing, and cardioprotective activity.

Nanoparticles have taken a firm hold on us. It has completely entered in our lives and is affecting us in every possible way. So, in this situation, the toxicity of ZnO nanoparticles can't be ignored. After being used in different industries, nanoparticles are directly discharged into the water bodies, which affects the aquatic life. Not only this excessive use of nanoparticles in textiles and cosmetics, but also in the biomedical field, can cause neurological toxicity and pose genetic risks. The toxicity of nanoparticles depends on their size, shape, concentration, time of exposure, etc., etc. There is a need to investigate strategies for synthesizing nanoparticles to minimize damaging effects on living organisms and the environment. There is a need to understand and research more in this field, so we will not harm our environment knowingly or unknowingly. We should not completely rely on these nanoparticles, but go for other better options.

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